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Deliverable D5.3

D-N4.3 Extended Test Description Method

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List of Abbreviations

CF	Control Function
DoE	Design of Experiments
ERP	Experiment Realisation Plan
ES	Experiment Specification
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
HES	Hybrid Energy Storage
HTD	Holistic Testing Description
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
MENB	Multi-domain Energy Network Benchmark
OuI	Object under Investigation
Pol	Purpose of Investigation
QS	Qualification Strategy
RI	Research Infrastructure
SC	System Configuration
SuT	System under Test
TC	Test Case
TS	Test Specification
UML	Unified Modeling Language
USAT	Uncertainty Structure Analysis Template

Executive Summary

With the increasing integration of Information and Communication Technology into energy systems and the convergence of various energy infrastructures, it has become necessary to define new testing scenarios, profiles, and processes. Achieving this requires a thorough review of major trends shaping research, testing, and validation practices, emphasizing emerging aspects such as interoperability testing and digitalization. ERIGrid 2.0 addresses these challenges through an iterative approach to developing testing scenarios, profiles, and processes.

This deliverable focuses on refining and enhancing testing processes, primarily advancing holistic test case procedures and test reporting methods. Three key extensions have been introduced:

- *Enhanced System and Control Function Descriptions:* Systems and control functions can now be documented in a much more detailed and structured manner. This structured, platform-independent description format offers significant benefits, including the ability to generate both simulation models and real laboratory tests from the same specifications. This format improves test reproducibility by enabling seamless conversion between simulation tools or lab environments.
- *Addressing Uncertainty in Experiments:* Recognizing the inherent uncertainties in both laboratory and simulation-based experiments, this deliverable introduces tools to support experimenters in systematically addressing these uncertainties during the planning stage. This includes (i) a new template for conducting systematic uncertainty structure analysis and (ii) enhancements to the existing Holistic Testing Description templates to incorporate uncertainty considerations throughout all experimental stages.
- *Online Test Case Repository:* To maximize the long-term utility of test cases developed within ERIGrid 2.0, an online repository has been established. Users can publish their Test Cases by uploading Word files to a GitHub repository, where they are converted into web pages and hosted for broader access. This repository ensures that the Test Cases will remain accessible and beneficial to users even after the conclusion of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

These advancements collectively aim to strengthen the processes of testing, validation, and research within evolving energy systems.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

Smart grid and energy systems solutions have become complex and multidisciplinary. With the further integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and integration with other energy systems, new testing scenarios, profiles, and processes must be defined. To achieve this, big trends affecting research, testing, and validation processes need to be reviewed, with a special focus on new aspects such as interoperability testing or digitalization. ERIGrid 2.0 addresses these issues through an iterative creation of testing scenarios, profiles, and processes.

This deliverable focuses on defining and improving testing processes. One of the main goals of this work was to extend the development of holistic test case procedures and test reporting methods. Furthermore, these procedures have been collected in a test case repository that will increase the re-usability of the collected test cases beyond the ERIGrid 2.0 project. The work reported in this deliverable was based on a collection of feedback and experience from different user groups, within and outside of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, to identify needs for the extension or clarification of the original holistic test case procedure. Based on the feedback, different updates and extensions to the holistic testing procedure were implemented. To help and guide users, an online test case repository was also introduced, where best practice test cases have been collected as inspiration for new and existing users.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the Holistic Testing Description (HTD) and its related procedures as well as an overview of the collected user feedback on possible improvements. In Section 3 the extensions that were developed in ERIGrid 2.0 are described. This is followed by selected examples that explain how the extensions should be used in Section 4. Finally, the deliverable is concluded in Section 5. Additional information is also provided in Appendix A and Appendix B.

2 Holistic Testing Procedure and User Feedback

2.1 Holistic Testing Description Approach

The Holistic Testing Description (HTD) approach comprises a set of textual templates (ERIGrid Consortium, 2019), a graphical notation and partial processes that may be employed by a practitioner to structure, refine and document their testing endeavour (Heussen et al., 2019). As with any model process, the HTD offers a supporting structure and raises relevant questions. Whereas users have reported benefits from using HTD templates in early phases of test scoping and planning, the fully documented test description may also be relevant in cases where a complete trace of the experiment design is valued (Heussen et al., 2019).

A common point of departure in applying the HTD should always be the formulation of a Test Case (TC), with its elements outlined in Figure 1. The HTD comprises further steps, reducing abstraction to the implementation in a physical or virtual testbed (Heussen et al., 2019).

ERIGrid Test Description Canvas

Title: _____ Author: _____
Date: _____

Test Objectives Why is the test needed? What do we expect to find out?		Purpose of Investigation (Pol) The test purposes classified in with terms <i>Characterization</i> , <i>Verification</i> , or <i>Validation</i>	
Object under Investigation (Oui) "the component(s) (1..n) that are to be qualified by the test"	Function(s) under Investigation (Fui) "the referenced specification of a function realized (operationalized) by the object under investigation"	System under Test (SuT) Systems, subsystems, components included in the test case or test setup.	Functions under Test (FuiT) Functions relevant to the operation of the system under test, including Fui and relevant interactions btw. Oui and SuT.
Domain under Investigation (Dui): "the relevant domains or sub-domains of test parameters and connectivity."			
Test criteria: Formulation of criteria for each Pol based on properties of SuT; encompasses properties of test signals and output measures.			
target metrics Measures required to quantify each identified test criteria	variability attributes controllable or uncontrollable factors and the required variability; ref. to Pol.	quality attributes threshold levels for test result quality as well as pass/fail criteria.	

K. Heussen 30-01-2020

Figure 1: Illustration of the Test Case elements as a canvas.

The steps and elements on the path to implementation of an experiment are outlined here in their logical sequence (Heussen et al., 2019):

- **Test Case (TC):** A TC structures the motivation for testing by combining narrative, graphical, qualitative, and quantitative elements to create a shared testing context. It consists of three main parts: the Test Objectives (in narrative and analytical forms), the description of system functions and components (organizing the System under Test (SuT)), and the Test

Criteria (formalizing test objectives through performance measures). Unlike use cases, TCs focus on both structural and functional aspects of the test system and its boundaries, emphasizing the isolation of test objectives from implementation details. A detailed TC is crucial for complex experiments and also serves as documentation and justification for testing campaigns.

- *Qualification Strategy (QS)*: The QS outlines how to achieve the qualification goals set in the TC through a series of experiments. It is particularly useful for complex experimental designs, such as round-robin testing, cross-validation of simulation results, or combining simulated and physical experiments. It can also include assessing testbed characteristics as an intermediate step in system testing, as reported in various studies.
- *Test Specification (TS)*: The TS outlines a detailed test design, including metrics, the configuration of the test system, its parameters, inputs, measurands, and test sequences. It is independent of the experimental platform and typically results from standard test planning activities, requiring minimal overhead. Key components include the configuration of the Test System, Input/Output parameters, and the metrics applied during testing.
- *Experiment Realisation Plan (ERP)*: To implement a TS in an experiment on a Research Infrastructure (RI), the TS requirements must be aligned with the capabilities of the RI, including hardware, software, and models. The high-level test design provides guidelines for identifying suitable RI and creating an ERP. The ERP offers a conceptual approach and potential algorithms for complex experiments with multiple testbeds or RI cooperations, but it is unnecessary for simple experiments where the experiment configuration directly follows from the TS.
- *Experiment Specification (ES)*: The ES details how the experimental platform (testbed) is configured to execute an experiment, mapping a single TS to the components, structure, and procedures of a given RI. In cases like round-robin experiments, one TS may be applied to multiple RI. Developed through collaboration between testbed experts and test managers, the ES documents the experiment setup, sequence, interfacing of the Object under Investigation (Oul) with the testbed, and the recording of results.
- *Results Annotation*: The collection and annotation of experiment results is a crucial part of any testing process. To maintain traceability across multiple testbeds, time resolutions, and data formats, it is recommended to use a common reference frame and format for organizing results. This framework can also apply to defining test signals and documenting system configurations. However, solutions for these challenges are typically domain-specific. In the energy systems context, organizing data often involves combining time series of measurements with static information, e.g. a grid model and other metadata, with relevant data formats available for reference.

Here, the TC, TS, and ES are based on templates. The QS and ERP are free form documents with a specific purpose in context of the proposed method.

2.2 User Feedback

To improve the HTD feedback from users was collected. The idea was to gather improvements for the original procedure as well as possible extensions. An overview of all collected issues is displayed in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview of collected issues for the Holistic Testing Description.

ID	Title	Type	Implem.
I1	HTD template layout	Improvement	No
I2	Drawing tool/template	Extension	No
I3	Extended system configuration description	Extension	Yes
I4	Description of control functions	Extension	Yes
I5	Description of simulation models	Extension	No
I6	HTD data format	Extension	No
I7	Extension of HTD for Uncertainty Representation	Extension	Yes
I8	FAIR HTD - Consistent Document Reference Specifications for HTD docs	Extension	No
I9	TC Canvas conversion	Extension	No
I10	Provide tool support for an online HTD repository	Improvement	Yes

Of the issues collected most were extensions to the original HTD method. From these three were selected for implementation: I3, I4, and I7. Furthermore, from the improvements, I7 was also selected for implementation. A description of each issue is found in the following sections. The implemented issues are further described in Section 3.

2.2.1 I1 – HTD Template Layout

A minor issue that could be considered for improving future versions of the templates is the layout. Currently, the space that is available to the user for writing the information is limited to the right half of the page. This causes some difficulties when large pictures or diagrams are inserted since their size is limited by the width of the writing area.

2.2.2 I2 – Drawing Tool/Template

One issue during drafting TCs is how the user can draw diagrams in a consistent and harmonised way as indicated in the guidelines. Complex diagrams including several components are rather hard to draw from scratch following the diagrams' convention from the guidelines and more often than not the users resort to other types of drawing tools.

A drawing tool or a template could substantially reduce the effort to draw the diagrams. Also, it would encourage all users to use the harmonised approach (components, terminals and domains) for these diagrams.

2.2.3 I3 – Extended System Configuration Description

System Configurations (SCs) can be quite complex. The original HTD template provides space for describing SCs, but it does not encourage users to make this in a structured way. Providing a list of components and a few overview figures is simply not enough in some cases.

One solution would be to add an optional template for SCs to the HTD. This could for instance be based on an adapted version of the SC template from the PreCISE approach from the SmILES project (Nguyen et al., 2018), which provides a structured approach for describing SCs. For complex setups, this could be added as an attachment to an HTD description.

2.2.4 I4 – Description of Control Functions

Control Functions (CFs) are an essential part of basically all setups described by HTD. However, even though the original HTD templates provide space for describing CFs, they do not encourage users to make this in a structured way.

This extension proposes to add to the HTD an optional template for CFs. This could for instance be based on an adapted version of the CF template from the PreCISE approach (Gehrke & Jensen, 2017b), which provides a structured approach for describing CFs. For setups with complex controllers, this could be added as an attachment to an HTD description.

2.2.5 I5 – Description of Simulation Models

The HTD has been used on several occasions to describe simulation setups. However, the templates do not provide proper support to describe simulation models. This can become a real issue when specific (properties of) models are subject of the TC. Providing a reference implementation (e.g., a Simulink model or PowerFactory model) is for several reasons, not a satisfying solution, rather a tool-independent description would be required.

This extension proposes to add to the HTD an optional template for simulation models. This could for instance be based on an adapted version of the model description template from the PreCISE approach (Widl et al., 2019), which provides a tool-independent approach for describing simulation models. For complex simulation setups this could be added as an attachment to an HTD description.

2.2.6 I6 – HTD Data Format

Setups described by the HTD are typically associated with some kind of input data (e.g., generation profiles). However, the HTD provides no means to distribute data consistently. If any data is provided, there is no guarantee that a recipient of an HTD description has the knowledge or the tools to interpret this data.

This extension proposes to define a format for attaching data to an HTD description. This could for instance be based on the data format used for the PreCISE approach (Gehrke & Jensen, 2017a), which provides a simple and machine-readable approach to share text-based data.

2.2.7 I7 – Extension of HTD for Uncertainty Representation

This proposal addresses extensions of the HTD to include uncertainty representation. The goal is to help experimenters in systematically addressing uncertainty aspects of their experiments, in case analysis and experiment design. The extensions are currently documented in the HTD word template and an Excel file with several sheets. The expected extensions would be:

- *Test Case*: Extended guidelines (text update),
- *Qualification Strategy*: Extended guidelines (text update),
- *Test Specification*: Extended guidelines (text update); reference to uncertainty analysis spreadsheet, and

- *Experiment Specification*: Re-organisation of fields; extended guidelines (text update); reference to uncertainty analysis spreadsheet.

2.2.8 I8 – FAIR HTD – Consistent Document Reference Specifications for HTD documents

The findability (i.e., according to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) principle) of HTD documents in a global context is currently not a given. Both in terms of version management and in terms of following a development history (e.g. I want to simplify my test design process and documentation by referencing a few 'parent' TCs). The following solutions are proposed:

- Consistent naming scheme for HTD templates (identifiers), and
- Additional fields for a) reference identifier and b) "parent HTD".

2.2.9 I9 – Test Case Canvas Conversion

There is a large number of TCs being formulated in conjunction with ERIGrid 2.0 Lab Access projects. However, the TCs are typically reported in the "canvas" form and not otherwise available. If made available, these would greatly enrich the portfolio of TCs, if used consistently.

Describe the solution you would like to provide for an automatic conversion of the TC Canvas as an alternative input format for the automatic HTML conversion.

Describe alternatives you have considered if the conversion is non-trivial with the existing template. Maybe a variant of the canvas template with proper tagging could be created and distributed to the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium.

2.2.10 I10 – Provide Tool Support for an Online HTD Repository

TCs can help users to implement laboratory tests. Therefore, it is important that previously created TCs can be easily shared between users. The current format using Word files requires file sharing. This makes it difficult to find TCs related to a certain topic since they are not easily searchable.

To improve this, an online repository of TCs can help. Created TCs can be published here and would then be browsable and searchable by other users.

3 Extensions of the Holistic Testing Procedure

3.1 Holistic Testing Procedure Tool Support

One of the goals of this work was to improve the reusability of TCs. The HTD developed in the ERIGrid project (Strasser & Sosnina, 2020) was based on a Word template and it was then up to the user how to publish this or make it available to other users. A disadvantage of this method is that it is difficult for other users to browse and search for information when this is only available in a file format. Therefore, the goal here was to create an online repository where the TCs can be published and browsed by other users.

Different options were discussed, such as creating a completely new approach where the HTD is moved completely online. In the end, the choice fell on an approach that allows easy online publication of TCs but at the same time stays backwards compatible with the old templates. The developed solution uses GitHub¹, GitHub Actions², and GitHub Pages³ to convert uploaded Word files into web pages. The workflow is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conversion of Test Case Word files to online repository.

The process starts with the upload of a file to the *test-case-repository-word-input* GitHub repository (*ERIGrid2/test-case-repository-word-input*, 2024). When triggered, all compatible Word files are collected. This can either be TCs written in the original template, see Section 2.1, or templates from one of the extensions, see Sections 3.2 to 3.4. Using the collected files, a new release is created in the repository. The release provides a link that can be used to access the collected files.

Once the release has been created, the *test-case-repository-word2md* repository is automatically triggered (*ERIGrid2/test-case-repository-word2md*, 2024). When a trigger is received, this repository downloads the Word files from the release in the previous step and converts these to a Markdown format. The code for this was written in Python, is open-source and can be found in the *test-case-repository-word2md* repository (*ERIGrid2/test-case-repository-*

¹<https://github.com/>

²<https://github.com/features/actions>

³<https://pages.github.com/>

word2md, 2024). In a nutshell, the script parses the Word files and translates any text into a Markdown format (Gruber, 2004). Any figures embedded in the Word document are extracted and saved in the same folder as the Word file. Once the conversion is completed a new release is created and the next repository is triggered.

The next repository in the workflow is the *test-case-repository* (*ERIGrid2/test-case-repository*, 2024). When this is triggered it downloads the Markdown files and the figures from the *test-case-repository-word2md* repository and converts these into Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) files. For this step Hugo⁴ is used. It allows easy conversion of Markdown files into a complete website using a template-based approach. Once the files have been converted they are hosted on GitHub Pages. The current version of the ERIGrid 2.0 Test Case Repository can be found here (*ERIGrid 2.0 Test Case Repository*, 2024).

3.2 System Configuration Extension

The System Configuration (SC) is the *static* part of an HTD description. It is intended to be a complete description of a technical system that includes a characterization of all key system components. Even though dynamic attributes (e.g., transient parameters) may be included, it does not contain information about the use of the system.

Previously, the HTD template contained just a short section for describing an SC. In the case of complex SCs, this posed a challenge for users to provide a clear and well-structured description, particularly in simulation studies involving extensive energy networks. Therefore, an optional extension of the HTD has been created, enabling users to provide a well-organized SC description using a separate, dedicated template.

The new template was created based on a similar form from the H2020 SmILES project (Nguyen et al., 2018). However, the focus has been put more on the description of technical (simulation) experiments and the experience from previous use was taken into account. Furthermore, the new template has been carefully structured in a way that allows to extract the contained information in an automated way and to translate it to other machine-readable formats (parsing and conversion by script).

Formally, the new SC template describes a set of components as well as their topological composition to form the system itself. The components are associated to terminals, which define how they interact with other components. The composition of components to systems is achieved by specifying the connections between these terminals, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Components, terminals and connection points in a System Configuration.

The new SC template document constitutes a reference description form to facilitate and set a standard for information exchange between stakeholders based on the following categories:

⁴<https://gohugo.io/>

- *General description*: Specifies a name and ID for the SC together with a short description of its context.
- *System Breakdown Diagram*: Provides a diagram that gives an overview of all types of elements that constitute the SC. The elements are represented as classes. They are organized on different branches of a tree to reflect different domains and they are related to each other on different levels (of detail). Relations between the elements are indicated in compliance with Unified Modeling Language (UML) notations.
- *Graphical representations*: Provides domain-specific graphical representations of the SC. This may include network diagrams or any other technical or non-technical drawings.
- *Terminal descriptions*: Specifies interfaces between objects (instances of classes) and relations between them (energy and/or information exchanges) via terminals.
- *Component descriptions*: Provides detailed information about all SC components. This includes information about the components' functionality and attributes, their interfaces to other elements, or their instances that are part of the SC.
- *Connection points*: Lists the connection points between all the component instances contained in the SC in terms of connections between terminals.

3.3 Control Functions Extension

A CF is a description of an embedded control system (or an aspect thereof) which, together with the inherent physical properties of the system itself, defines the behaviour of the control system and its response to dynamic input. Control functions can be seen as a further detailing, or more formal description, of the mechanisms governing the behaviour of individual actors in a use case.

Previously, the HTD template did not explicitly contain a section for describing an CF. Therefore, an optional extension of the HTD has been created, providing a dedicated template to facilitate and set a standard for information exchange between stakeholders on the definition of a CF.

Similar to the case of the SC template, the CF description form was created based on a similar template from the H2020 SmILES project (Gehrke & Jensen, 2017b). Again, technological (simulation) experiments were emphasized, previous experience was incorporated, and machine readability is now supported.

The new CF template covers the following categories:

- *Functional Description*: Provides a brief introduction to the problem solved by the function or the algorithm. The technical background is outlined by giving an overview of the function or algorithm.
- *Terminology* (optional): Allows the definition of specific terms and concepts to be used throughout the document.
- *Methodology*: Explain the methodology or theory of the function or algorithm in detail. All information necessary for understanding the specifics of the function or algorithm, especially for translating it into software, must be included. Required equations and computations should be described and explained term by term and be closely related to the detailed description of the function or algorithm later in the document.

- *Limitations*: Describes prerequisites for the CF. These include limitations caused by input data, special types of data required, limitations inherent to the function or algorithm, and any other problems known to be associated with the function or algorithm.
- *Inputs*: Describes data inputs to the CF. This includes static input data such as configuration or parametrization as well as dynamic input data such as measurement data or events.
- *Outputs*: Describes data output produced by the CF, insofar as the output is relevant to the interaction between the function or algorithm and the rest of the system. This covers mostly dynamic output data such as setpoints or events.
- *Use Cases*: Provides use cases that demonstrate the proper use and express the functional requirements of the CF.
- *Diagrams*: Contains diagrams (data flow diagrams, sequence diagrams, logic diagrams, state diagrams, control hierarchy, etc.) which capture the data flow occurring between a CF and the rest of the system. These diagrams should reveal relationships among and between the various components in a program or system.
- *Algorithmic Functions* (optional): Contains the description of algorithms in a step-by-step fashion, preferably using pseudocode if applicable.
- *Deterministic / Stochastic Functions* (optional): Contains a mathematical description of the deterministic/stochastic part of a CF. Each mathematical formula should be followed by a brief explanation of the symbology.
- *Deployment* (optional): Provides additional information regarding the deployment of the CF in a hardware and/or software setup. It should be filled in if the described function or algorithm is deployed in a concrete setup (e.g., as part of a lab experiment).

CFs may take the form of mathematical functions, such as transfer functions or descriptions of a stochastic process, or they may be best described by an algorithm. These different forms require different description options. As a result, some of the categories listed above are optional because their content does not apply to all descriptions.

3.4 Uncertainty Representation

Experiments, both laboratory and simulation-based, are riddled with uncertainties and incertitude. The uncertainties may be caused by noise and natural fluctuations in input and system parameters, uncertainty of the true value of hardware parameters, or an uncertainty related to the fidelity of a simulation model, to name a few. Such uncertainties often cause challenges for the reproducibility of test results, since deterministic exact reproduction is often impossible in practice. To support reproducibility, one should therefore consider an uncertainty-aware documentation of experiments. A systematic approach to the analysis and accounting of uncertainty factors could carry significant value for the research infrastructure and energy research communities when the reproducibility of laboratory tests can be extended with the proper handling of uncertainties. To document and account for uncertainty characteristics, there is, however, a wide range of philosophical and mathematical frameworks available.

To aid experimenters in documenting their consideration of uncertainty during experimental planning, the holistic test description has been extended in two areas. First, an additional template or tool was developed to support systematic uncertainty structure analysis and experimental design. Second, the existing HTD templates have been reinforced to cover uncertainty

aspects in all stages by adding a few fields and as well as revised guidelines for the full template.

An overview of the uncertainty analysis extensions and an associated workflow is illustrated in Figure 4. Details on the new uncertainty structure analysis template and the HTD uncertainty amendments are described in Section 3.4.1 and Section 3.4.2, respectively.

Figure 4: The existing three-level structure of the Holistic Testing Description (left) frames the Uncertainty Structure Analysis Template (centre/yellow lines), linking to several of the Holistic Testing Description template fields in all three Holistic Testing Description layers. The Uncertainty Structure Analysis Template is designed to facilitate the application of Design of Experiments methods, uncertainty quantification and scalability analysis (right).

The main changes to the HTD are documented in Deliverable D-JRA1.2 (Schwarz, Schulte, et al., 2024), which also offers background on uncertainty concepts and methods, examples and guidelines to the approach. Up-to-date versions of the HTD template and the supporting Uncertainty Structure Analysis template are made available at the HTD repository (*ERIGrid2/holistic-test-description*, 2024).

3.4.1 Uncertainty Structure Analysis Template

The new Uncertainty Structure Analysis Template (USAT), has been introduced in the form of a spreadsheet tool with multiple interlinked sheets, supporting a detailed analysis of a given Test Case toward a suitable factor prioritization in terms of the Design of Experiments (DoE) approach. The main purpose of the USAT is to support the systematic breakdown of uncertainty aspects considering uncertainty aspects in the separate HTD layers:

- (a) *Test purpose* Purpose of Investigation (PoI) viewpoint: Do I want to find out something about uncertainty, or do I just aim to ensure the robustness of test results?
- (b) *Problem structure* in the SC viewpoint: What aspects of my system configuration and parameters introduce uncertainty to the testing problem?
- (c) *Research Infrastructure* in the ES viewpoint: What uncertainty issues are typical for a chosen type of setup and what types of uncertainty sources should be considered?

The tool offers several built-in support functions, considering the need to categorize types of uncertainty aspects found in the different layers, e.g. by linking uncertainty types with appropriate representations (in the Parameter Analysis sheet), by linking parameters with target measures (PoI viewpoint), and by identifying typical uncertainty challenges for a range of experimental setup types (ES viewpoint).

Finally, the tool supports an experimental design approach by linking target measures and system parameters and sequencing the refinement of the parameter analysis, leading directly to a *factor screening* and *factor ranking* analysis in the sense of a multi-stage DoE approach.

3.4.2 Uncertainty Annotations in the HTD

While the USAT tool may be used independently of the HTD, it links back directly to the HTD templates. The amended and existing set of HTD fields facilitate the description of uncertainty aspects as follows:

- The *Test Case (TC)*, section of *test criteria*: the existing fields *variability attributes* and *quality attributes*. *Variability attributes* are used to identify uncontrollable (external) factors, and with *quality attributes*, a statistical success metric for the test can be formulated. An additional field *Detailed PoI and Factor Analysis* refers to the new uncertainty structure analysis template.
- The guidelines for the *Qualification Strategy* have been extended to include an uncertainty identification and management strategy.
- The *Test Specification (TS)* fields *Input and output parameters* and *Sources of uncertainty* are moved together and can be linked to the detailed uncertainty structure analysis template.
- For the mapping to research infrastructure, the *Experiment Realisation plan* can link back to the USAT sheet “ES viewpoint”, since the trade-offs regarding uncertainty aspects in various experimental setups may be considered.
- The *Experiment Specification (ES)* now addresses uncertainty in several fields, directly linking to USAT “ES viewpoint” columns: two new fields up *Experimental Setup uncertainties* (new), *Precision of equipment*, *Measurement Uncertainty* (new), *Uncertainty Management* (new).

4 Collection of Best Practice Examples

4.1 Selected Examples

4.1.1 System Configuration

The SC description selected as an example in this document has been developed as part of a reference setup for multi-domain energy network simulations (D'Arco et al., 2022). This reference setup intends to inspire the use of co-simulation for the assessment of multi-energy systems.

The level of detail was chosen in a way that allows to apply different modelling approaches for the individual subsystems. For instance, the thermal network could be implemented either in a quasi-static model (series of equilibrium states) or a dynamic model (hydraulic transients). However, the template allows to provide a detailed description of the SC that is independent of any modelling approach, enabling the implementation of the related test case in any appropriate simulation tool.

4.1.2 Control Function

The SC used as an example above includes a heat pump. A hydraulic pump controls the mass flow in the heat pump's condenser loop, where cold water is drawn from the bottom of a storage tank, heated up in the heat pump's condenser and fed back at the top of the tank.

In the related test case, the operation of the heat pump is limited by a power consumption setpoint (coming from a voltage controller). The controller specified in this example regulates the mass flow rate through the heat pump's condenser loop via the hydraulic pump such that this power consumption setpoint is met.

This is a simple example for applying the CF description template to a well-known type of controller (PID controller), used to demonstrate how the template should be applied properly. However, the template can also be used to describe more complex control schemes (like the voltage controller or the flex heat controller in the multi-domain energy network reference setup).

4.1.3 Uncertainty Representation

Several examples illustrate the application of the uncertainty extensions of the HTD and the USAT. These examples are included in the ERIGrid 2.0 HTD repository (*ERIGrid2/holistic-test-description*, 2024).

- The HTD illustration example, the “Light Dimmer” has been extended with a case for uncertainty consideration in the fields *TC/quality attributes* and *TS/source of uncertainty*.
- The multi-domain energy network model above, (D'Arco et al., 2022), exemplifies the use of HTD fields *TC/Variability attributes*, *TC/quality attributes* and *TS/Source of uncertainty* and *ES/Experimental Setup uncertainties*.
- For the same Multi-domain Energy Network Benchmark (MENB), an extensive screening has been performed for potential uncertainty parameters; the annotations illustrating the use of the tool are reported in the sheets *USAT/Pol Viewpoint*, *USAT/SC Definition* &

Diagrams, and the sheet *USAT/SC Parameter Analysis*. This example demonstrates the complete four steps of the tool, incl. the factor screening and ranking for a selected PoI.

- A case of a Hybrid Energy Storage (HES) system, the isolated use of the USAT tool is illustrated, i.e. without the associated HTD template; the associated experimental design and analysis was reported in (Schwarz, Perez, Pham, Heussen, & Tran, 2024).

It is worth noting that the USAT sheet *SC Definition & Diagrams* builds on the System Breakdown Diagram method from the SC extension reported here. For simple cases, an illustration SC can be reported directly (as in the HES example), whereas more complex system configurations benefit from a separate illustration of the system breakdown diagram (as in MENB example).

4.2 Best Practices and Guidelines

The improvements to the HTD presented above allow a better description of test cases and allow for a better reproducibility of the test results. They give users the possibility to go into much more detail than it was possible before. Combining this with the new online repository, test cases can help even more researchers in creating successful tests. To help users even more, some guidelines are presented here on how the new extensions are intended to be used. Of course, there is a limitation and also no obligation to use the extensions.

The new SC template is meant to be used for test setups involving complex system configurations, e.g., in simulation studies involving large energy networks. The section designated to SC description in the main HTD template should be utilized anytime the system configuration is simple enough to be described in just a few sentences and illustrated with a single sketch. Otherwise, the new SC description template should be filled and attached to the main HTD document.

In addition, the new CF template is intended to be used for test setups involving sophisticated controllers, e.g., energy management systems or embedded controllers. Using only the main HTD template in case only well-known devices are used (e.g., PID controllers) that require no further explanation for the recipient of the HTD description. Otherwise, the new CF template should be filled and attached to the main HTD document for every type of controller included in the test setup.

When uncertainty issues emerge as a concern in test planning, the related sections in the test case should be filled in carefully. This may be related to input parameters, relevant environmental influences, the test setup itself, or the experimental infrastructure. As a first step, this should be done by simply expressing, qualitatively, the specific uncertainty aspect in the respective field (e.g. when the confidence of the test result needs to be quantified, note this in “quality attributes”; if test system inputs are variable and uncertain, note this under “variability attributes”).

The new Uncertainty Structure Analysis Templates (USATs) should be used as a tool especially when the uncertainty treatment is not obvious, when several factors or system parameters carry uncertainty, or if the lab setup has uncertainty issues. The associated steps and sheets simplify the experiment planning. In such cases, also the guidelines in (Schwarz, Schulte, et al., 2024) may offer useful consultation.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable provides an extended test description method for smart grid test cases. It builds on the HTD from the ERIGrid project (Heussen et al., 2019) and within ERIGrid 2.0 it has been extended to allow for a better description of TCs.

First of all, systems and control functions can now be described in much more detail and in a much more structured format than before. This has several advantages. The new templates provide a platform-independent description format for both the system and the controllers. Based on this format, both simulation models and real lab tests can be created. This also increases the reproducibility of the tests since the platform-independent format allows for easier conversion between simulation tools or different lab environments.

Secondly, both laboratory and simulation-based experiments contain uncertainties and incertitude. This deliverable presents an extension that supports experimenters in documenting their consideration of uncertainty during experimental planning. This extension is split into two tools: an additional template to support systematic uncertainty structure analysis and the existing HTD templates have been reinforced to cover uncertainty aspects in all stages.

Another goal in ERIGrid 2.0 was to improve the reusability of TCs. The goal was to create an online repository where the TCs can be published and browsed by other users. To publish a TC, the Word file is uploaded to a GitHub repository where it is then converted into a webpage and finally hosted. The current version of the ERIGrid 2.0 TC Repository can be found here (*ERIGrid 2.0 Test Case Repository*, 2024). With the new repository, it is the goal that the TCs developed will continue to support users also after the ERIGrid 2.0 project has ended.

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Appendix A: System Configuration

Appendix A.1 Template

System Configuration Description Form (v1.0)

This document constitutes a reference description form to facilitate and set a standard for information exchange between stakeholders on the definition of a system configuration (SC). The SC is the "static" part of a system description. Even though dynamic attributes (e.g., transient parameters) may be included, it does not contain information about the use of the system.

The SC is a detailed technical description of a system and its inherent properties. Formally, an SC comprises a set of components. These components are associated to terminals, which define how they interact with other components. The composition of components to systems is achieved by specifying the connections between these terminals.

NOTE: This document has been carefully structured in a way that allows to extract the contained information in an automated way and to translate it to other machine-readable formats (parsing and conversion by script). Therefore, when editing this document, please keep the following in mind:

- Only information (text and figures) provided in the cells of the tables defined below will be extracted.
- The first cell of each table contains a specific title that identifies its purpose ("Document History", "System Configuration Identification", etc.). Do NOT change these titles, even if you replicate a table (as in the case for the element descriptions).
- When extending tables (e.g., add more instances to an element description), insert new row with the same layout. Especially do NOT split or merge cells in a table's row.
- You may add additional (sub-)headings to structure the document to accommodate your needs.
- Names and identifiers should be machine-readable, i.e., no spaces, no special symbols, only basic ASCII letters and numbers.

1. Document History

Please keep track of significant changes to this document. Consider using the following versioning scheme to indicate the stage of the SC: 0.x – concept stage, 1.x – test design stage, 2.x – post test / documentation stage, 3.x and higher – revisiting the test.

Document History			
Date	Version	Description	Author

2. General description

2.1 System configuration identification

Please specify a name for this SC together with an ID to identify it.

NOTE: Please use a machine-readable ID.

System Configuration Identification	
System configuration ID	Name

2.2 Short description of context

Please provide a short description of the SC's context in the table below. This will help readers understand what the SC is intended for and for what kind of test cases it relevant. Optionally, an ontology / namespace associated with the component and variable naming may be referenced.

Short Description of Context
Context description
Key figures
Keywords
Ontology / namespace (optional)

3. System Breakdown Diagram (SBD)

Please add in the table cell below the System Breakdown Diagram (SBD), which gives an overview of all types of elements that constitute the SC. The elements are represented as classes. They are organized on different branches of a tree to reflect different domains and they are related to each other on different "levels" (of detail). There exist two types of "vertical" relations between a level (n) class and a level (n+1) class. Their representation in the SBD is compliant with UML notations:

- **Containment relation:** a class "has a" sub-class. Containment relations are depicted with a filled diamond (on the side of the container class) and a solid line (example: a rotor is part of a generator).
- **Inheritance relation:** a sub-class "is a" subtype of its parent class. Inheritance relations are depicted with an unfilled triangle (on the side of the parent class) and a solid line. Inheritance relations suppose a transfer of the descriptive parameters from the parent class to the inherited class (example: an underground cable is a type of electric interconnection).

Every class in the SBD should have an alphanumeric tag, to which it can be referred to in the list of SC elements further down below.

For further details please refer to [this document](#) (p. 13ff).

NOTE: Please use only machine-readable names for class names and tags.

System Breakdown Diagram
<add figure here>

4. Graphical representations of SC

Please provide domain-specific graphical representations of the SC in the table cells below. This may include network diagrams or any other technical or non-technical drawings.

NOTE: Please put each drawing in a separate table cell. Each table cell with a drawing should be preceded by a table cell containing the drawing's title.

Graphical Representation of System Configuration
Overview
<add figure here>
Detailed view (optional)
<add additional figures here, replicate this and the preceding cell if required>

5. Terminal descriptions

In the SBD only "vertical" relations between classes (containment or inheritance) are depicted. "Horizontal" connections to further specify interfaces between objects (instances of classes) and relations between them (energy and/or information exchanges) are defined via terminals.

NOTE: Please use only machine-readable names for type IDs.

Terminal Description				
Name	Type ID	Type of exchange	Connected component classes	Comment

6. Component descriptions

Please replicate the table below for each of the elements described in the SBD. This table provides detailed information an element, for instance about its functionality and attributes, its interfaces to other elements, or its instances that are part of the SC.

NOTE: Please use only machine-readable names for IDs, tags, attribute names, etc.

Component description	
Tag in SBD	
Level in SBD	
Class ID	
Parent class	

Contained in		
Description		
Number of components in SC		
Attributes		
Functionality		
Physical characteristics		
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	

7. Connection points

Please list the connection points between all the component instances contained in the SC in the table below.

Connection points			
Connection from component	Connection from terminal	Connection to component	Connection to terminal

Appendix A.2 Example

System Configuration Description Form (v1.2)

1. Document History

Document History			
Date	Version	Description	Author
2021-03-23	0.1	First draft version	Edmund Widl (AIT)
2021-05-17	0.2	Add quasi-static thermal network system configuration	Christopher Wild (DTU)
2021-09-01	0.3	Add additional information for the electric network configuration	Tran The Hoang (CEA)
2021-11-19	1.0	Update system configuration to the final implemented benchmark setup	Edmund Widl (AIT)
2022-11-11	1.1	Adapt to ERIGrid 2.0 SC template: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • focus on testing / simulation • make template parseable • improved SBD 	Edmund Widl (AIT)

2. General description

2.1 System configuration identification

System Configuration Identification	
System configuration ID	Name
MENB-SC	System configuration for the multi-energy network benchmark

2.2 Short description of context

Short Description of Context
<p>Context description</p> <p>The system configuration described in this document has been developed as part of a reference setup for multi-domain energy network simulations. This reference setup intends to inspire the use of co-simulation for the assessment of multi-energy systems.</p> <p>The level of detail was chosen in a way that allows to apply different modelling approaches for the individual subsystems. For instance, the thermal network could be implemented either in a quasi-static model (series of equilibrium states) or a dynamic model (hydraulic transients).</p> <p>The system configuration resembles part of the sub-urban area of a typical Central European city. The climate is typical for Central Europe with its moderately warm summers and cold winters. Solar irradiation ranges between 800 and 1200 kWh/m². Ambient ground temperature is constant at 8°C.</p>
<p>Key figures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • electrical network: 2 consecutive lines (0.3 km each), connected to external grid • thermal network: 3 main consecutive pipes (supply and return, 0.5 km each), connected to external grid

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> power-to-heat facility: 1 heat pump (max. 100 kW_{el}) connected to a thermal tank (100 m³) feeding into the thermal network consumption: 2 consumers, each representing the aggregated loads (electrical and thermal) of an urban quarter and connected to both networks generation: 2 PV systems (one of 150 kW_{el, peak} and one of 50 kW_{el, peak})
Keywords
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> local consumption of high PV generation decentralized heat generation heat pumps coupled heat and electric networks
Ontology / namespace (optional)
N/A

3. System Breakdown Diagram (SBD)

4. Graphical representations of SC

5. Terminal descriptions

Terminal Description				
Name	Type ID	Type of exchange	Connected component classes	Comment
Heat connector	Heat-Connection	heat flow (water mass flow)	ExternalElectricGrid, Line, Busbar, Load, PVSystem, HeatPump	connects components of the thermal network
Electric power connector	Electric-Connection	electric power flow (electric current)	ExternalThermalGrid, Pipe, Junction, Bypass, HeatExchanger, Tank, HeatPump, Pump	connects components of the electrical network
Measurement connector	Measure-Connection	measurement exchange (communication signal)	Bus, Tank, HeatPump, VoltageController, FlexHeatController	connects sensors with controllers via a communication link
Control connector	Ctrl-Connection	control signal exchange (communication signal)	Pump, HeatPump, VoltageController, FlexHeatController	connects controllers with actuators via a communication link

6. Component descriptions

6.1 Electrical network

Component description		
Tag in SBD	1	
Level in SBD	1	
Class ID	ElectricNetwork	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	MENB-SC	
Description	This element represents an electric distribution network. It contains interconnected components with the purpose of delivering electricity to the consumers.	
Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	The electrical network's actual functionality is determined by its components. This class serves as logical unit containing these components and has itself no functionality.	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
-	-	-
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
el_net	-	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	1.1
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	ExternalElectricGrid
Parent class	-
Contained in	el_net
Description	This element represents a connection to an external electrical grid supplying the local electrical distribution network.
Number of components in SC	1
Attributes	

Functionality	The external grid controls the voltage and the phase angle of the busbar to which it is connected.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f (float) - Nominal frequency [Hz] • v_n (float) - Nominal voltage [kV] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
plug_ext	ElectricConnection	connection point of the electrical distribution network to the external grid
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
ext_el_grid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • f [Hz]: 220 • v_n [kV]: 0.4 	

Component description		
Tag in SBD	1.2	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Line	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	el_net	
Description	This element represents a power line of an electrical distribution network.	
Number of components in SC	2	
Attributes		
Functionality	The power lines transport electricity between the busbars of an electrical network.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l (float): line length [km] • r (float): resistance [Ω/km] • x (float): reactance [Ω/km] • c (float): capacitance [nF/km] • max_i (float): rated current [kA] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
plug_line_a	ElectricConnection	connection to a bus of the electrical distribution network on one side of the power line

plug_line_b	ElectricConnection	connection to a bus of the electrical distribution network on other side of the power line
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
line_1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.3 • r [Ω/km]: 0.306 • x [Ω/km]: 0.29 • c [nF/km]: 13.2 • max_i [kA]: 0.35 	
line_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.3 • r [Ω/km]: 0.306 • x [Ω/km]: 0.29 • c [nF/km]: 13.2 • max_i [kA]: 0.35 	

Component description		
Tag in SBD	1.3	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Busbar	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	el_net	
Description	This element represents an electrical busbar used in substations for local power distribution.	
Number of components in SC	2	
Attributes		
Functionality	The electrical busbars connect the components of the electrical network (lines, loads, PV systems).	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • vn (float) - nominal voltage [kV] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
plug_bus	ElectricConnection	connection point to other components (lines, loads, PV systems) of the electrical distribution network
meas_voltage_pu	MeasureConnection	voltage measurement (for the voltage controller) [p.u.]
Instances		

Instance ID	Instance parameterization
bus_1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vn [kV]: 0.4
bus_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vn [kV]: 0.4

Component description		
Tag in SBD	1.4	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Load	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	el_net	
Description	This element represents a component of the electrical network that consumes (active) electric power.	
Number of components in SC	3	
Attributes		
Functionality	Each load represents an aggregation of the (active) power consumption of several consumers (e.g., households connected to an LV feeder).	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vn (float): nominal voltage [kV] p (float): nominal active power consumption [kW] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
plug_load	ElectricConnection	connection to a bus of the electrical distribution network through which power is consumed
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
load_1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vn [kV]: 0.4 p [kW]: 120 	
load_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vn [kV]: 0.4 p [kW]: 45 	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	1.5
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	PVSystem
Parent class	-

Contained in	el_net	
Description	This element represents a PV system comprising several PV panels.	
Number of components in SC	2	
Attributes		
Functionality	The PV systems generates electrical power and supplies it to the electrical distribution network via a busbar connection. Its generation profile is independent of the network conditions.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P_peak (float): peak production [kW] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
plug_pv	ElectricConnection	connection to a bus of the electrical distribution network through which the generated power is delivered to the electrical network
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
pv_1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P_peak [kW]: 150 	
pv_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P_peak [kW]: 50 	

6.2 Thermal network

Component description	
Tag in SBD	2
Level in SBD	1
Class ID	ThermalNetwork
Parent class	-
Contained in	MENB-SC
Description	This element represents the thermal network that delivers a mass flow of hot water to satisfy the heat demand of the connected consumers.
Number of components in SC	1
Attributes	
Functionality	The thermal network's actual functionality is mostly determined by its components. This class serves as logical unit containing these components and has itself no functionality.
Physical characteristics	-

Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
-	-	-
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
th_net	-	

Component description		
Tag in SBD	2.1	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	ExternalThermalGrid	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	th_net	
Description	This element represents a connection to an external higher-level thermal network supplying the local thermal network.	
Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	The external thermal network acts as a pressure source with a prescribed supply temperature. It is considered an ideal heating unit without any constraints regarding mass flow or ramp rates.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • p_ext (float): pressure of the external thermal network [bar] • T_supply_ext (float): nominal supply temperature [°C] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_supply	HeatConnection	supply line connection to external thermal grid
flange_return	HeatConnection	return line connection to external thermal grid
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
ext_th_grid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • p_ext [bar]: 6 • T_supply_ext [°C]: 75 	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	2.2
Level in SBD	2

Class ID	Pipe	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	th_net	
Description	This element represents a straight pipe with constant cross section used to transport water within the thermal network.	
Number of components in SC	14 (7x supply, 7x return)	
Attributes		
Functionality	Determines the transport effects (pressure drop, flow delays, etc.) for a mass flow based on hydraulic principles. Depending on the insulation of the pipe and the surrounding temperature, the temperature of the water transported through the pipe changes.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l (float): pipe length [km] • d (float): pipe diameter [m] • alpha (float): heat transfer coefficient [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$] • k (float): roughness of pipe material [mm] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_a	HeatConnection	connection to another component of the thermal network on one side of the pipe
flange_b	HeatConnection	connection to another component of the thermal network on other side of the pipe
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
pipe_1_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01 	
pipe_1_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01 	
pipe_2_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01 	
pipe_2_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [$\text{Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01 	

pipe_4_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_4_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.5 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_tank_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_tank_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_3_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_3_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_5_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_5_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_6_supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01
pipe_6_return	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • l [km]: 0.01 • d [m]: 0.1 • alpha [Wm⁻²K⁻¹]: 1.5 • k [mm]: 0.01

Component description	
Tag in SBD	2.3

Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Junction	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	th_net	
Description	This element represents a tee junction for connecting three pipes.	
Number of components in SC	6	
Attributes		
Functionality	Used either for splitting the mass flow from a single pipe into separate mass flows of two pipes or joining mass flows from two separate pipes into a single mass flow for one pipe. Splitting/joining follows basic hydraulic rules (e.g., mass conservation).	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_1	HeatConnection	connection to pipe 1
flange_2	HeatConnection	connection to pipe 2
flange_3	HeatConnection	connection to pipe 3
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
junction_1_supply	(branch-off from supply line to consumers)	
junction_2_supply	(branch-off from supply line to consumers)	
junction_1_return	branch-off from return line to consumers	
junction_2_return	branch-off from return line to consumers	
junction_tank_supply	branch-off from supply line to tank	
junction_tank_return	branch-off from return line to tank	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	2.4
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	HeatExchanger
Parent class	-
Contained in	th_net
Description	This element represents a heat exchanger acting as an aggregated heat consumer in the thermal network.
Number of components in SC	2

Attributes		
Functionality	The heat exchanger is fed with hot water from the thermal network's supply line. The mass flow through the heat exchanger is adjusted to reach a pre-defined return temperature, depending on the current heat demand from the aggregated consumer.	
Physical characteristics	T_return_target (float): set-point for return temperature [°C]	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_supply	HeatConnection	inlet of heat exchanger from supply line
flange_return	HeatConnection	outlet of heat exchanger to return line
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
hex_1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_return_target [°C]: 40 	
hex_2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_return_target [°C]: 40 	

Component description		
Tag in SBD	2.5	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Bypass	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	th_net	
Description	This element represents the bypass of the thermal network.	
Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	Ideal valve that allows to regulate the water mass flow from the supply line to the return line independently of the consumers.	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_supply	HeatConnection	inlet of bypass from supply line
flange_return	HeatConnection	outlet of bypass to return line
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
bypass	-	

6.3 Power-to-heat facility

Component description		
Tag in SBD	3	
Level in SBD	1	
Class ID	PowerToHeatFacility	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	MENB-SC	
Description	This element represents a power-to-heat facility comprising a heat pump connected to a thermal tank, which feeds into the thermal network's supply line to support its operation. By consuming local excess PV generation, the power-to-heat facility can be used at the same time to improve the stability of the electrical network and support the supply of the thermal network. Its components are actuated by the flex heat controller.	
Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	The power-to-heat facility's actual functionality is determined by its components. This class serves as logical unit containing these components and has itself no functionality.	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
-	-	-
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
p2h	-	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	3.1
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	HeatPump
Parent class	-
Contained in	p2h
Description	This element represents a heat pump with constant condenser output temperature.

Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	The source for the evaporator is the thermal network's return line. The condenser's output is fed to the thermal storage tank.	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <code>P_rated_max</code> (float): electrical power rating of compressor [kW_{el}] • <code>P_rated_min</code> (float): minimal electrical power consumption for operating the compressor [kW_{el}] • <code>P_0</code> (float): electrical stand-by power consumption [kW_{el}] • <code>T_evap_min</code> (float): minimal evaporator outlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] • <code>T_cond_max</code> (float): maximum condenser outlet temperature [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] • <code>T_cond_target</code> (float): condenser outlet temperature setpoint [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] • <code>eta_sys</code> (float): ratio between work provided by the pump and available thermodynamic work [-] • <code>eta_comp</code> (float): compressor efficiency [-] • <code>lambda_comp</code> (float): compressor time constant [s^{-1}] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
<code>plug_load</code>	ElectricConnection	connection to a bus of the electrical distribution network through which power is consumed
<code>flange_evap_in</code>	HeatConnection	inlet of heat pump evaporator from return line
<code>flange_evap_out</code>	HeatConnection	outlet of heat pump evaporator to return line
<code>flange_cond_in</code>	HeatConnection	inlet of heat pump condenser from tank
<code>flange_cond_out</code>	HeatConnection	outlet of heat pump condenser to tank
<code>meas_p_el</code>	MeasureConnection	measurement of electrical power consumption (for flex heat controller) [kW_{el}]
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
<code>hp</code>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <code>P_rated</code> [kW_{el}]: 100 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P_0 [kW_{el}]: 0.3 • T_evap_min [°C]: 20 • T_cond_max [°C]: 85 • T_cond_target [°C]: 75 • eta_sys [-]: 0.5 • eta_comp [-]: 0.7 • lambda_comp [s⁻¹]: 0.2
--	--

Component description		
Tag in SBD	3.2	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Tank	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	p2h	
Description	This element represents a stratified hot water storage tank.	
Number of components in SC	1	
Attributes		
Functionality	<p>The tank has two hydraulic loops (also see pumps below):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cold water is drawn from the bottom of the tank, heated up by the heat pump and fed back at the top of the tank • hot water is drawn from the top of the tank and fed to the heating network's supply line; simultaneously an equal amount of cold water is drawn from the heating network's return line to refill the tank 	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • V (float): tank volume [m³] • h (float): height of tank (without insulation) [m] • d (float): thickness of insulation [m] • k (float): specific heat conductivity of insulation [Wm⁻¹K⁻¹] • N (int): number of volume segments [-] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_tank_supply	HeatConnection	hot water outlet of tank to supply line
flange_tank_return	HeatConnection	cold water inlet from return line to tank
flange_hp_out	HeatConnection	cold water outlet from tank to heat pump condenser
flange_hp_in	HeatConnection	hot water inlet from heat pump condenser to tank

meas_temp	MeasureConnection	tank temperature measurement (for flex heat controller) [°C]
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
tank	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • V [m³]: 100 • h [m]: 9.2 • d [m]: 0.1 • k [Wm⁻¹K⁻¹]: 0.03 • N [-]: 10 	

Component description		
Tag in SBD	3.3	
Level in SBD	2	
Class ID	Pump	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	p2h	
Description	This element represents a water pump with prescribed mass flow rate.	
Number of components in SC	2	
Attributes		
Functionality	<p>Ideal water pump that generates a mass flow according to the setpoint. Moves the water in the following loops of the power-to-heat facility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • condenser loop: pump hot water from the heat pump condenser to the tank • network support loop: pump hot water from the tank to the supply line 	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
flange_in	HeatConnection	pump inlet
flange_out	HeatConnection	pump outlet
setpoint_mflow	CtrlConnection	set-point for pump mass flow (from flex heat controller)
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	

pump_cond	pump for tank charging loop
pump_tank	pump for tank discharging loop

6.4 Controls

Component description		
Tag in SBD	4	
Level in SBD	1	
Class ID	Controller	
Parent class	-	
Contained in	MENB-SC	
Description	This element serves as parent class for concrete controller implementations.	
Number of components in SC	-	
Attributes		
Functionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controllers govern the operation of the system. 	
Physical characteristics	-	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
-	-	-
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
-	-	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	4.1
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	VoltageController
Parent class	Controller
Contained in	-
Description	This element represents a voltage controller in the electrical distribution network.
Number of components in SC	1
Attributes	

Functionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This controller monitors the voltage at bus_1 and proposes a power consumption setpoint for the heat pump (controllable/flexible load) to keep the voltage within acceptable limits. 	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> delta_vm_up (float): upper threshold for turning off the heat pump [p.u.] delta_vm_low_hp_on (float): lower threshold for turning on the heat pump [p.u.] delta_vm_low_hp_off (float): lower threshold for turning off the heat pump [p.u.] delta_vm_deadband (float): deadband size [p.u.] hp_p_el_mw_min (float): minimum operating point (minimal allowed power consumption) of heat pump [MWe] k_p (float): the controller's proportional term [-] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
meas_voltage_pu	MeasureConnection	voltage measurement at bus_1 [p.u.]
setpoint_hp_p_el	CtrlConnection	proposed heat pump setpoint for electrical consumption [MWe]
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
voltage_ctrl	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> delta_vm_up [p.u.]: 0.1 delta_vm_low_hp_on [p.u.]: -0.1 delta_vm_low_hp_off [p.u.]: -0.08 delta_vm_deadband [p.u.]: 0.03 hp_p_el_mw_min [kW_{el}]: 35 k_p [-]: 0.15 	

Component description	
Tag in SBD	4.2
Level in SBD	2
Class ID	FlexHeatController
Parent class	Controller
Contained in	-
Description	This element represents a dedicated controller for operating the power-to-heat facility.
Number of components in SC	1

Attributes		
Functionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The flex heat controller decides whether the heat supply is covered entirely through the external grid or whether the power-to-heat facility supports by discharging the tank. If required, the heat pump is used to charge the tank, taking into account the power consumption threshold from the voltage controller (i.e., the power consumption never exceeds the setpoint, but may be less). 	
Physical characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_tank_max (float): maximum tank temperature [°C] T_tank_min (float): minimum tank temperature [°C] mdot_tank_out_setpoint (float): setpoint for tank discharge mass flow rate [kg/s] 	
Terminals		
Terminal ID	Type ID	Description
meas_tank_temp	MeasureConnection	measurement of tank temperature [°C]
meas_hp_p_el	MeasureConnection	measurement of electrical power consumption of heat pump [kW _{el}]
setpoint_hp_p_el	CtrlConnection	setpoint for power consumption of heat pump from voltage controller [MW _{el}]
setpoint_tank_mflow	CtrlConnection	setpoint for tank discharge mass flow [kg/s]
setpoint_cond_mflow	CtrlConnection	setpoint for heat pump condenser mass flow [kg/s]
Instances		
Instance ID	Instance parameterization	
flex_heat_ctrl	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> T_tank_max [°C]: 72 T_tank_min [°C]: 65 	

7. Connection points

Connection points			
Connection from terminal	Connection from terminal	Connection from terminal	Connection from terminal
ext_el_grid	plug_ext	line_1	plug_line_a
bus_1	plug_bus	line_1	plug_line_b
bus_1	plug_bus	line_2	plug_line_a

bus_1	plug_bus	load_1	plug_load
bus_1	plug_bus	hp	plug_load
bus_1	plug_bus	pv_1	plug_pv
bus_2	plug_bus	line_2	plug_line_b
bus_2	plug_bus	load_2	plug_load
bus_2	plug_bus	pv_2	plug_pv
ext_th_grid	flange_supply	pipe_1_supply	flange_a
ext_th_grid	flange_return	pipe_1_return	flange_b
junction_tank_s upply	flange_1	pipe_1_supply	flange_b
junction_tank_s upply	flange_2	pipe_tank_suppl y	flange_b
junction_tank_s upply	flange_3	pipe_2_supply	flange_a
junction_tank_r eturn	flange_1	pipe_2_return	flange_b
junction_tank_r eturn	flange_2	pipe_tank_retur n	flange_a
junction_tank_r eturn	flange_3	hp	flange_evap_in
junction_1_supp ly	flange_1	pipe_2_supply	flange_b
junction_1_supp ly	flange_2	pipe_3_supply	flange_a
junction_1_supp ly	flange_3	pipe_4_supply	flange_a
junction_1_retu rn	flange_1	pipe_4_return	flange_b
junction_1_retu rn	flange_2	pipe_3_return	flange_b
junction_1_retu rn	flange_3	pipe_2_return	flange_a
junction_2_supp ly	flange_1	pipe_4_supply	flange_b
junction_2_supp ly	flange_2	pipe_5_supply	flange_a
junction_2_supp ly	flange_3	pipe_6_supply	flange_a
junction_2_retu rn	flange_1	pipe_6_return	flange_b
junction_2_retu rn	flange_2	pipe_5_return	flange_b
junction_2_retu rn	flange_3	pipe_4_return	flange_a

hex_1	flange_supply	pipe_3_supply	flange_b
hex_1	flange_return	pipe_3_return	flange_a
hex_2	flange_supply	pipe_5_supply	flange_b
hex_2	flange_return	pipe_5_return	flange_a
hp	flange_evap_out	pipe_1_return	flange_a
hp	flange_cond_in	pump_cond	flange_out
hp	flange_cond_out	tank	flange_hp_in
hp	meas_p_el	flex_heat_ctrl	meas_hp_p_el
tank	meas_temp	flex_heat_ctrl	meas_tank_temp
tank	flange_hp_out	pump_cond	flange_in
tank	flange_tank_return	pipe_tank_return	flange_b
tank	flange_tank_supply	pump_tank	flange_in
pump_tank	flange_out	pipe_tank_supply	flange_a
bypass	flange_supply	pipe_6_supply	flange_b
bypass	flange_return	pipe_6_return	flange_a
voltage_ctrl	meas_voltage_pu	bus_1	meas_voltage_pu
voltage_ctrl	setpoint_hp_p_el	flex_heat_ctrl	setpoint_hp_p_el
flex_heat_ctrl	setpoint_tank_mflow	pump_tank	setpoint_mflow
flex_heat_ctrl	setpoint_cond_mflow	pump_cond	setpoint_mflow

Appendix B: Control Functions

Appendix B.1 Template

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

This document constitutes a reference description form to facilitate and set a standard for information exchange between stakeholders on the definition of a **control function (CF)**. The CF is a description of an embedded control system (or an aspect thereof) which, together with the inherent physical properties of the system itself, defines the behavior of the control system and its response to dynamic input. Control functions can be seen as a further detailing, or more formal description, of the mechanisms governing the behavior of individual actors in a use case.

Control functions may take the form of mathematical functions, such as transfer functions or descriptions of a stochastic process, or they may be best described by an algorithm. These different forms require different description options. As a result, some of the sections of the document are optional because their content does not apply to all descriptions. This is indicated at the beginning of each section. Optional sections should be left blank, rather than being deleted entirely, in order to preserve the consistency of section numbers. Sections marked as mandatory must be filled in every case.

NOTE: This document has been carefully structured in a way that allows to extract the contained information in an automated way and to translate it to other machine-readable formats (parsing and conversion by script). Therefore, when editing this document, please keep the following in mind:

- Only information (text and figures) provided in the cells of the tables defined below will be extracted.
- The first cell of each table contains a specific title that identifies its purpose ("Document History", "Functional Description", etc.). Do NOT change these titles, even if you replicate a table (as in the case for the control function inputs).
- When extending tables (e.g., add more instances to an element description), insert new row with the same layout. Especially do NOT split or merge cells in a table's row.
- You may add additional (sub-)headings to structure the document to accommodate your needs.
- Names and identifiers should be machine-readable, i.e., no spaces, no special symbols, only basic ASCII letters and numbers.

1. Document History

Please keep track of significant changes to this document. Consider using the following versioning scheme to indicate the stage of the CF: 0.x – concept stage, 1.x – test design stage, 2.x – post test / documentation stage, 3.x and higher – revisiting the test.

Document History			
Date	Version	Description	Author

2. Control Function Identification

Please specify a name for this CF together with an ID to identify it.

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

NOTE: Please use a machine-readable ID.

Control Function Identification	
Control Function ID	Name

3. Functional Description

The purpose here is to provide a brief introduction to the problem solved by the function or the algorithm. The technical background should be outlined by giving an overview of the function or algorithm. It will be important in the early introduction of the document to clearly inform the reader on the intent of the function or algorithm as well as the problem the function or algorithm is addressing. The author should keep in mind that this document is not a technical paper and should be written in such a way that it can be understood by an audience with limited expertise in specific simulation domains.

The statement of the problem should include a clear statement outlining the problem and why the problem is important and needs to be addressed. It should contain a sketch of the problem/situation and, if known and/or relevant, the background history that led to the development of the function or algorithm, including why the problem was investigated and how it relates to earlier work that has been done in the field. It should show that the author thoroughly understands the problem.

Functional Description

4. Terminology (optional)

The role of terminology is important, and it defines concepts used in the scientific document. The definitions should be made precise, concise, and unambiguous. Each term should be used in one and only one way throughout the document.

Terminology	

5. Methodology

This section is used to provide the methodology or theory of the function or algorithm in detail. Relevant research results should be referenced. The description should not be as detailed as a peer-review journal paper. However, all information necessary for understanding specifics of the function or algorithm, especially for translating it into software, must be included. Required equations and computations should be described and explained term by term and be closely related to the detailed description of the function or algorithm later in the document.

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

In case of well-known or standard functions or algorithms, a simple reference to the theory (e.g., a link to the Wikipedia page for "PID controller") is sufficient.

Methodology

6. Limitations

This section describes prerequisites for the function or algorithm. These include limitations caused by input data, special types of data required, limitations inherent to the function or algorithm, situations where the function or algorithm cannot be applied, potential implementation difficulties, and any other problems known to be associated with the function or algorithm. This section should also describe both the implementation and operational impacts of these limitations.

Limitations

7. Inputs

Please replicate the table below for each control input. This table describes data inputs to the documented function or algorithm. This includes static input data such as configuration or parametrization as well as dynamic input data such as measurement data or events. Each input data element should specify the data type (e.g., floating point, integer, character string), units (e.g., degrees, percentages), valid ranges (e.g., 0 to infinity; -1.0 to +1.0 inclusive), the expected update rate of the data (e.g., static; 10Hz; daily) and a short description of the information the variable contains (e.g., "width of the radar beam in degrees ...").

All data element names should be self-descriptive (i.e., the name should describe what the data element contains). Widely recognized symbols from textbooks and professional literature are acceptable.

NOTE: Please use machine-readable names.

Control Function Input	
Name	
Type (according to SC description)	
Unit	
Range	
Expected update rate	
Description	

8. Outputs

Please replicate the table below for each control output. This table describes data output produced by the documented function or algorithm, insofar as the output is relevant to the interaction between the function or algorithm and the rest of the system. This covers mostly dynamic output data such as

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

setpoints or events. Each output data element should describe the format of the output data in sufficient detail for downstream algorithms to be easily interfaced. This should as a minimum include the data type (e.g., floating point, integer, character string), units (e.g., degrees, percentages), valid ranges (e.g., 0 to infinity; -1.0 to +1.0 inclusive), the expected update rate of the data (e.g., static; 10Hz; daily) and a short description of the information the variable contains (e.g., "power setpoint in kW").

All data element names should be self-descriptive (i.e., the name should describe what the data element contains). Widely recognized symbols from textbooks and professional literature are acceptable.

NOTE: Please use machine-readable names.

Control Function Output	
Name	
Type (according to SC description)	
Unit	
Range	
Expected update rate	
Description	

9. Use Cases

Use Cases are a way to express functional requirements. They bridge the gap between user needs and system functionality by directly stating the user's intention and system response for each step in a particular interaction. No single Use Case specifies the entire requirements of the system. A Use Case itself is an interaction that a User or another System has with the system that is being designed to achieve a goal. Different scenarios within a Use Case show how the goal succeeds or fails. A success scenario is one in which the goal is achieved; a failure scenario is one where the goal is not achieved. Because the goals summarize the intention of the various uses of the system, the users can see how they are supposed to use the system. Users can also spot when the system does not support all of their goals without having to wait for the first prototype or having to wait for the system to be developed.

This is a summary of how to write Use Cases:

- The name of the use case should start with a strong verb.
- A Use Case is a set of scenarios. A scenario is a list of steps.
- Each step should state what the user does and/or how the system responds.
- The steps must not mention how the system does something.
- Each step needs to be analyzed in detail before it becomes code.
- Keep It Simple: use the simplest format you need.
- Keep track of different versions.
- Writing use cases is a team sport.
- Focus on a particular user (give them a name).

Don't get bogged down in all the special ways it can go wrong until you've finished the main success story.

Control Function
Description Form (v1.0)

Use Case Example	<Use Case name>
Date created	
Actor	
Description	
Preconditions	
Postconditions	
Priority	
Frequency of use	
Normal course	
Alternative course	
Exceptions	
Assumptions	
Notes and issues	

10. Diagrams (data flow diagrams, sequence diagrams, logic diagrams, state diagrams, control hierarchy, etc.)

This section will contain diagrams which capture the data flow occurring between a function or algorithm and the rest of the system. These diagrams should reveal relationships among and between the various components in a program or system.

In case of distributed controllers, i.e., multiple processes communicating to achieve an overall objective, sequence diagrams of the interaction between the individual processes must be provided here, in addition to the detailed descriptions of the individual processes in subsequent sections.

Where applicable, this section should also contain Logic Diagrams and/or State Diagrams. Logic Diagrams represent logical concepts and State Diagrams represent the behavior of a system. State diagrams describe all the possible states of an object as events occur. Each diagram usually represents objects of a single class and tracks the different states of its objects through the system.

NOTE: Please put each drawing in a separate table cell. Each table cell with a drawing should be preceded by a table cell containing the drawing's title.

Diagrams
<Diagram title>

11. Algorithmic Functions (pseudocode)

This section is optional; however, at least one of the three detailed description sections (Deterministic Functions, Stochastic Functions, Algorithmic Functions) must be filled in.

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

This section will contain the description of algorithms in a step-by-step fashion, preferably using pseudocode if applicable.

The term “pseudocode” is used here to describe an English-like language that articulates the steps carried out in an algorithm. It allows the author to focus on the logic of the algorithm without being distracted by details of any given programming language’s syntax. For the sake of completeness and consistency, pseudocode should follow a general syntax convention (see the appendix). Pseudocode can be augmented with natural language where convenient.

In case of distributed controllers, i.e., multiple processes communicating to achieve an overall objective, sequence diagrams of the interaction between the individual processes must be provided in the “Diagrams” section, in addition to the detailed descriptions of each of the individual processes here.

NOTE: Please put each algorithm in a separate table cell. Each table cell with an algorithm should be preceded by a table cell containing the algorithm’s title.

Algorithms
<Algorithm title>

12. Deterministic Functions

This section is optional; however, at least one of the three detailed description sections (Deterministic Functions, Stochastic Functions, Algorithmic Functions) must be filled in.

This section will contain a mathematical description of the deterministic (as opposed to stochastic) part of a function. Each mathematical formula should be followed by a brief explanation of the symbology.

The section can also be used to document the mathematical background of an algorithm for which pseudocode is provided in the “Algorithms” section below. In this case, the description should also cover the method used to realize the implementation in the Algorithms section.

Deterministic Functions

13. Stochastic Functions

This section is optional; however, at least one of the three detailed description sections (Deterministic Functions, Stochastic Functions, Algorithmic Functions) must be filled in.

This section will contain a mathematical description of the stochastic (as opposed to deterministic) part of a function. Each mathematical formula should be followed by a brief explanation of the symbology.

The section can also be used to document the mathematical background of an algorithm for which pseudocode is provided in the “Algorithms” section below. In this case, the description should also cover the method used to realize the implementation in the Algorithms section.

Stochastic Functions

Control Function
Description Form (v1.0)

14. Deployment (optional)

This section is optional. It should be filled in if the described function or algorithm is deployed in a concrete setup (e.g., as part of a lab experiment).

This section provides additional information regarding the deployment of the control function in a hardware and/or software setup.

Deployment (optional)

15. References

References

Appendix B.2 Example

Control Function Description Form (v1.0)

1. Document History

Date	Version	Description	Author
2023-04-03	0.1	first draft	Edmund Widl (AIT)
2024-01-25	0.2	Added identification	Filip Pröbstl Andrén (AIT)

2. Control Function Identification

Control Function Identification	
Control Function ID	Name
MENB-CF-PID	PID controller for the hydraulic pump

3. Functional Description

Functional Description
<p>Background: System configuration MENB-SC includes a heat pump. A hydraulic pump controls the mass flow in the heat pump's condenser loop, where cold water is drawn from the bottom of a storage tank, heated up in the heat pump's condenser and fed back at the top of the tank.</p> <p>Problem formulation: The operation of the heat pump is limited by a power consumption setpoint (coming from a voltage controller). The controller specified in this document regulates the mass flow rate through the heat pump's condenser loop via the hydraulic pump such that this power consumption setpoint is met.</p>

4. Terminology (optional)

Terminology	
PID controller	A proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller is a control loop mechanism employing feedback that is widely used in applications requiring continuously modulated control. A PID controller continuously calculates an error value $e(t)$ as the difference between a desired setpoint (SP) and a measured process variable (PV) and applies a correction based on proportional, integral, and derivative terms (denoted P, I, and D respectively).

5. Methodology

Methodology
This control function implements a PID controller .

6. Limitations

Limitations
N/A

 Control Function
 Description Form (v1.0)

7. Inputs

Control Function Input	
Name	meas_hp_p_el
Type (according to SC description)	MeasureConnection
Unit	kW _{el}
Range	[0, 100]
Expected update rate	1 Hz
Description	measurement of electrical power consumption of heat pump

Control Function Input	
Name	setpoint_hp_p_el
Type (according to SC description)	CtrlConnection
Unit	MW _{el}
Range	[0, 0.15]
Expected update rate	every 5 min
Description	setpoint for power consumption of heat pump from voltage controller

8. Outputs

Control Function Output	
Name	setpoint_cond_mflow
Type (according to SC description)	CtrlConnection
Unit	kg/s
Range	[0, 10]
Expected update rate	1 Hz
Description	setpoint for heat pump condenser mass flow

9. Use Cases

Use Case Example	Heat pump operation
Date created	2023-04-03
Actor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PID controller • hydraulic pump • heat pump

Control Function
Description Form (v1.0)

Description	The mass flow through the heat pump’s condenser loop is determined by the operation of the hydraulic pump. With the help of a PID controller (see Figure 1) the mass flow of the hydraulic pump is regulated.
Preconditions	The power consumption setpoint for the heat pump is not zero.
Postconditions	N/A
Priority	medium
Frequency of use	1 Hz
Normal course	The mass flow through the hydraulic pump is regulated using the heat pump’s power consumption as process variable and a setpoint (see Figure 1). PID controller parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • $K_p = 1e-4$ • $T_i = 10\text{ s}$ • $T_d = 10\text{ s}$
Alternative course	In case the power consumption setpoint of the heat pump is set to zero, the hydraulic pump is switched off. The PID output is then set to zero, resulting in zero mass flow rate.
Exceptions	N/A
Assumptions	N/A
Notes and issues	N/A

10. Diagrams

11. Algorithmic Functions (pseudocode)

Algorithms
Controller algorithm
N/A

12. Deterministic Functions

Deterministic Functions
<p>Error value:</p> $e(t) = \text{meas_hp_p_el}(t) - \text{setpoint_hp_p_el}(t)$ <p>Control variable:</p> $\text{setpoint_cond_mflow}(t) = K_p \left[e(t) + 1/T_i \int_0^t e(\tau) d\tau + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \right]$

13. Stochastic Functions

Stochastic Functions
N/A

14. Deployment

Deployment
<p>A state-of-the-art pneumatic PID controller device is used for the deployment (see Figure 2).</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 2: PID controller device (source: Wikipedia)</p>

15. References

References
N/A

Consortium

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